

DEVELOPMENT OF NUCLEAR ENERGY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article covers the development of nuclear energy in Uzbekistan. The author also concludes that nuclear energy is actively developing and in the medium term we should expect a powerful rise in the nuclear industry in developing countries that are experiencing an increasing need for energy resources.

Keywords: nuclear industry, nuclear energy, ecology, energy complex, Uzbekistan.

With the development of industry and other sectors, mankind discovers new sources of energy that are less detrimental to the environment, more energy-efficient and do not require the depletion of exhaustible natural resources, in connection with which the study of the development of nuclear energy is becoming relevant.

Nuclear energy is a branch of energy that produces electrical and thermal energy by converting nuclear energy.

The advantages of nuclear energy include: environmental friendliness, since nuclear energy does not contribute to the creation of a greenhouse effect; it is worth noting the enormous energy capacity of the fuel used (uranium), as well as the possibility of its reuse and, most importantly, uranium is a relatively inexpensive fuel; maintenance of nuclear power plants is a very important process, but it does not need to be carried out as often as refueling and maintenance of traditional power plants.

The disadvantages include the following: nuclear reactor waste remains radioactive for many years; Fissile nuclear materials falling into the wrong hands could lead to nuclear terrorism or blackmail, and uranium mining and enrichment could expose workers to radioactive dust and release that dust into the air or water.

Throughout the world, uranium is the main resource for the operation of nuclear power plants. At the same time, the world leaders in uranium reserves, Australia and Kazakhstan, do not have a well-developed nuclear energy industry. Uranium ore deposits are not evenly distributed across the globe. Today, only 28 countries in the world mine valuable raw materials in their subsoil and only 19 world powers produce uranium. The bulk - 88% of the

world's uranium reserves in the world are located in 10 countries, in the remaining 18 countries, some crumbs of 10% of fuel [2]. On July 19, 2018, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop nuclear energy in the Republic of Uzbekistan", a state administration body authorized to develop and implement a unified state policy and strategic directions in the field of nuclear energy development was created - the Agency for the Development of Nuclear Energy (Agency "Uzatom"), the main tasks and areas of activity of which are defined as:

- preparation of proposals on priority areas of state policy in the sphere of peaceful use of atomic energy, including development of regulatory legal acts;
- development and implementation of state programs for development of atomic energy in the Republic of Uzbekistan, attraction of investments, including foreign ones, for implementation of projects in the field of atomic energy;
- conclusion of agreements and contracts on design, construction and operation of atomic energy facilities with introduction of modern technologies and equipment that meet international requirements of industrial and environmental safety;
- preparation and implementation of comprehensive measures for development of atomic science and nuclear technologies, projects of fundamental research, scientific and survey, experimental design and innovation works, introduction of advanced technologies;
- ensuring development and safe operation of research and power atomic reactors, nuclear physics installations, storage facilities for nuclear materials and radiation sources, disposal of radioactive waste;
- improvement of the radiation and nuclear safety system of the republic's facilities with development of an action plan for prevention of nuclear accidents and radiation emergencies, jointly with other ministries and departments;
- ensuring the non-proliferation of nuclear materials and technologies, radioactive materials, implementing measures for physical protection and ensuring nuclear and radiation safety;
- organizing a system of training, retraining and advanced training of personnel, including in leading foreign institutes;
- implementing international cooperation and interaction with the International Atomic Energy Agency, the European Atomic Energy Community and other international organizations;
- developing, together with interested ministries and departments, cooperation with international financial institutions, donor countries,

companies and banks in order to attract foreign investment and advanced technologies in the field of nuclear energy [3].

President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev and President of Russia Vladimir Putin commented on the construction of a small nuclear power plant in Uzbekistan during their statements for the media on May 27: "Almost all leading countries of the world ensure their energy security and sustainable development through nuclear energy. Having large domestic uranium reserves and exporting it to third countries, this project is vital for us if we think about the prospects for entering a new stage of development of Uzbekistan", Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized.

Thus, President Vladimir Putin stated that the signing of the protocol on amendments to the intergovernmental agreement of 2018 "opens up the possibility of constructing a small-capacity nuclear power plant in Uzbekistan using modern Russian technologies that meet the most stringent safety and environmental protection requirements".

By decree of the President of Uzbekistan, the Agency for Atomic Energy is being created on the basis of the Agency for the Development of Nuclear Energy, which is being transferred from the structure of the Ministry of Energy to the Cabinet of Ministers. The Agency received the right to conclude direct contracts with companies, create business entities, and finance projects in the economy. In addition, a Committee for Industrial, Radiation and Nuclear Safety is being created, which will be responsible for safety policy at nuclear power and nuclear technology facilities, as well as at hazardous industrial facilities.

Back in early May, First Deputy Minister of Energy - Director of the Agency for the Development of Nuclear Energy (Uzatom) Azim Akhmedkhadjaev noted in an interview with Gazeta.uz that negotiations with Russia on the construction of a nuclear power plant in Uzbekistan were ongoing. "We are now simply negotiating, general words for now, nothing specific," he said, noting that the parties were discussing various areas of cooperation. Before this, Minister of Energy Jurabek Mirzamakhmudov indicated in an interview with Daryo that meetings and negotiations with Russia's Rosatom were ongoing. "Considering that this is a very large strategic project, there is no need to rush, everything needs to be weighed, measured not 7 times, but 77 times. After a full analysis and calculations, we can submit a report to the government and the president," the head of the Ministry of Energy noted. Kazakhstan is also planning to hold a referendum on the issue of building a nuclear power plant.

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